

INSTITUTIONAL QUALITY AND LIFE EXPECTANCY IN LOW-INCOME SUB-SAHARA AFRICAN COUNTRIES

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Abstract

With numerous research on institutional quality and human development, little has been done to access the impact of institutional quality on life expectancy in Low-income sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries. The problem facing SSA especially the low-income SSA countries are enormous. The problems include weak institutions which have to do with poor rule of law, corruption, bureaucratic authority which is addressed in this paper and the issue of life expectancy looking at health condition of the people and longevity. The objective of this study is to address the role of institutional quality on life expectancy in those countries from 2013 to 2022. The research used secondary data sourced from World Bank governance indicators and transparency international. The method of analysis adopted is panel data using the panel corrected standard error and generalized method of moment. The analysis produced a priori expectation. The findings are in line with theory. Both static and dynamic methods on institutional quality and life expectancy model indicates that most of the countries examined shows inclusive result in terms of rule of law, corruption, bureaucratic quality and property rights. As a result the study recommends policies to address corruption in all spheres of economic activities. Also, rule of law need to be implemented to the later and educational sector given a priority to promote development in the region.

Keywords: Institutional quality, Standard of living, Corruption, Rule of law, Property rights, Generalized method of moment, Sub-Saharan Africa countries.

JEL Classification: O15, O43, O5

INTRODUCTION

Specifically institutional quality as a concept in economics has been particularly influenced by the work of Douglass North, a Nobel Laureate in economics. According to [1]; [2] institutions are manmade rules that are imposed to guide and evaluate the attitude and behavior of people and also to determine the level of their interaction to ascertain the degree of commitment to the growth and development of the society. They are made up of formal constraints such as laws, regulation and constitutions and informal constraints such as taboos, values, customs, and traditions. In other words, institutions are structured within which human interactions take place either positively or otherwise. It is important to note that macroeconomic performance is influenced by institutional quality variables such as rule of law, property rights, corruption, and bureaucratic quality [3].

Institutional failure occurs when the structure of state apparatus itself causes rather than reduce uncertainty [4]. In the African context, institutional quality is not well entrenched, in terms of implementing proper rule of law, control of inflation and bureaucratic quality. All these affect the standard of human development in the region to the extent that, there is poor allocation of fund to human capital development. Also, due to high level of corruption, funds being allocated to educational sector are not judiciously utilized to develop the human

resources as proposed. This is a common practice in SSA countries, which negates the ideal socio-political and economic environment where economic activities could thrive [5].

On the other hand, strong institutions are the reverse of the weak. This means that strong institutions entail an economic environment with formidable and reliable institutional indices that bring about human development, doing business free from government renege process [6]. In a broad sense, institutions are expected to facilitate the generation of ideas, define property rights and contract, stimulate innovation, lower transaction cost, correct government failure, reduce uncertainty, foster efficiency and enhance economic performance [4, 5, 7, 8].

[9] opine that people in most developing countries suffer from poorer health and live shorter lives, on average, than people in rich countries. Accordingly, in 2005, average life expectancy at birth in Japan was 82 years compared to 35 years in Botswana and Lesotho [9]. It is important to note that, in the health development quality dimension, there are five indicators. The indicators are the following: Life expectancy at birth, Infant mortality rate, Physicians, Immunization of children, and CO₂ emissions per capita. The CO₂ indicator shows an environmental aspect, which may lead to degradation of health conditions.

A few existing studies do consider a role for informal institutions or social capital in explaining cross-country differences in income or health status. [10] analyses the effect of culture on per capita output across regions in European countries, but his paper also includes some cross-country regressions examining relationships between different indicators of culture and governance, that is formal institutions. Tabellini's measure of culture includes survey-based information on the extent of trust, whether people believe children should be taught to respect others, whether they should be taught to be obedient [11]. Tabellini's paper makes a strong case for the relevance of values and behavioural norms in explaining different experiences of economic development, but it does not adopt a deep determinants perspective, as neither formal institutions nor geographical characteristics are included as regressors explaining regional per capita income.

The approach adopted by Ahlerup, Olsson, and Yanagizawa (2008) as cited in [10], is the most closely related to [9], in that the explanatory variables in their model include a measure of formal institutions (covering bureaucratic quality, law and order, and corruption), social capital (measured as generalized trust) and their multiplicative interaction. Nevertheless, the focus of their cross-country empirical analysis is on explaining the growth of GDP per capita (from 1995-2005) or the rate of investment, not health status.

Also, rather than using a deep determinants approach; they fit a Barro-type growth regression that includes base-period income, investment prices and human capital proxied by life expectancy [12]. Their results imply that formal institutions and trust are substitutes in terms of enhancing growth; consequently, social capital has a stronger positive effect on growth for countries with lower quality formal institutions.

Furthermore, there is also a more extensive literature reviewed in [13], that examines the effect of social capital across countries on health indicators, including life expectancy. These studies normally do not control for formal institutions and geography; instead, proximate determinants, such as immunization rates, the number of doctors and income per capita, are often included as control variables. Also, [14] used a sample of 112 countries (which is representative of a wide range of absolute income governance indicators from World Bank

governance indicator for the years 1996, 1998 and, 2000. Using OLS, [14] found that institutional quality has an effect on life expectancy.

In accordance with the previous studies, [15]; [8] examines the impact of institutional quality on life expectancy at birth that will bring about economic growth for 21 OECD countries using panel data for the period of 1970-2010 in the context of panel co-integration and causality tests and Sub-Sahara Africa countries Two different model specifications are considered for this purpose. The variable of life expectancy which serve as an indicator of health and real per capita gross domestic product as an indicator of standard of living. While the independent variables are, real exports, real fixed capital and energy use per capita. Using [16] on co-integration tests, it indicates that there is a long-run relationship between the variables.

In order to deal with panel OLS, Pedroni dynamic OLS (DOLS) and fully modified OLS (FMOLS) techniques, employed by Maddala-Wu (1999) the estimated coefficient for life expectancy is found positive and statistically significant. Also, the results of panel Granger causality tests based on panel vector autoregressive (VAR) models indicates that there is a unidirectional causality running from life expectancy to real per capita GDP. Thus, income per capita, education, and public access to health care improve life expectancy at birth, whereas income inequality has an adverse effect on this measure of health. According to [15], the failed national and international programs of economic and structural adjustment policies that have not addressed the crucial issue of political structure are testimony to the importance of freedom and democracy for human well-being and health status.

[15]; [17] asserted that healthcare administration explains cross-country differences in levels and growth rates of income. In this paper, panel data analysis in the content of co-integration and causality relationship was provided for 21 OECD countries ranging from 1990-2010. The data was derived from World Bank's World development indicators, 2012. Also, panel co-integration test developed by [16] was used. The results show that life expectancy has a positive and statically significant effect on real per capita GDP.

METHODOLOGY

In terms of methodology and to avoid the potential difficulties of endogeneity and serial correlation are controlled by adopting both the static and dynamic panel data analysis. In other words, unlike previous studies that used fixed and random effect panel analysis only. Here the study used both fixed and random with generalised method of moments (GMM). All these serve as my contribution to the existing body of knowledge.

Based on the explanation above, this paper adapted the equation used by Klomp and Haan (2013) with modification by introducing other variable life expectancy which makes it different from previous studies. In their work, they estimated the relationship between political factors and human capital. In this work, institutional quality and life expectancy served as both the independent and dependent variables. Additionally, instrumental variable are inclusive in the models to burst the efficiency of the results and they are; government expenditure, school expenditure, health expenditure, infrastructural facilities and labour force. Accordingly, structural equations are used as a statistical technique to analyse the dimensions of a latent construct and analyse the dependence structure [18].

Structural equation model is characterized by two basic components; the measurement model, which allows using several variables (or indicators) for a single latent independent to dependent variable and the structural model, which relates independent to dependent variables. [19] came up with better measures that include more information and to determine whether human capital and political institutions have a multidimensional character stated in their model as thus,

$$[1.1] HC_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_j X_{ij} + \theta_i \text{Political}_i + \delta_i + \varepsilon_i$$

Where, HC_{it} is a measure for human capital (advanced or basic) of country j . As far as this work is concerned is replaced with human development and its three components measures like, standard of living, educational attainment and life expectancy which formed the dependent variables in the article. While political variable is replaced with institutional variables like rule of law, corruption, bureaucratic quality and property rights which also formed the independent variables with control variables.

Nevertheless, this study used both static and dynamic panel data analysis. These include random and fixed effects and the generalized method of moments. The GMM estimator is developed by Anderson and Hsiao [20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26] all for dynamic models of panel data.

The models are formally stated in conjunction with the objectives of the research as shown in Equation [1.1] for static models and Equation [1.2] – Equation [1.3] for dynamic models respectively. This is consistent with [24, 27, 28]. However both the static and dynamic structured equations are stated as follows. The structured equations for the static panel data can be specified as follows

$$[1.2] \quad LEX_{it} = \phi_1 + \phi_2 RLI_{it} + \phi_3 CI_{it} + \phi_4 BQ_{it} + \phi_5 PRI_{it} + \phi_6 GE_{it} + \phi_7 INFR_{it} + \phi_8 LAB_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

While the dynamic equations are also stated in terms of aggregated and disaggregated.

Aggregated Model;

$$[1.3] \quad LEX_{it} = \beta_{3i} + \phi_1 LEX_{it-1} + \phi_2 RLI_{it} + \phi_3 CI_{it} + \phi_4 BQ_{it} + \phi_5 PRI_{it} + \phi_6 HE_{it} + \phi_7 INFR_{it} + \phi_{10} LAB_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Disaggregated Model

$$[1.4] \quad LEX_{it} = \beta_{3i} + \phi_1 LEX_{it-1} + \phi_2 RLI_{it} + \phi_3 CI_{it} + \phi_4 BQ_{it} + \phi_5 PRI_{it} + \phi_6 HE_{it} + \phi_7 INFR_{it} + \phi_{10} LAB_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where,

<i>HDI</i>	=	Human Development Index (Percentage)
<i>PCY</i>	=	Per Capita Income (Per Capita GDP USD)
<i>EDU</i>	=	Educational Attainment (School enrolment %)
<i>LEX</i>	=	Life Expectancy (at Birth %)
<i>RLI</i>	=	Rule of Law (%)
<i>CI</i>	=	Corruption (%)
<i>BQ</i>	=	Bureaucratic Quality (%)
<i>PRI</i>	=	Property Right (%)
<i>HE</i>	=	Hospital Expenditure (Percentage of GDP)
<i>SE</i>	=	School Expenditure (Percentage of GDP)
<i>GE</i>	=	Government Expenditure (Percentage of GDP)
<i>LAB</i>	=	Labour Force (working age population over total population)
<i>INFR</i>	=	Infrastructural Facilities (Percentage of GDP)

RESULTS

Table 1: *Institutional Quality and Life Expectancy: Random Effect*

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	z-value	Prob> z
Constant	4.080	0.032	126.51	0.000
<i>RLI</i>	0.002	0.003	4.61	0.000*
<i>CI</i>	-0.006	0.004	-1.17	0.243
<i>BQI</i>	-0.003	0.005	-0.61	0.539
<i>PRI</i>	-0.037	0.006	-5.76	0.000*
<i>HE</i>	-0.023	0.007	3.37	0.001*
<i>LAB</i>	0.005	0.004	1.13	0.257
<i>INFR</i>	0.000	1.780	11.76	0.000*
Diagnostic statistics:				
R ² : Within	0.432			
Between	0.057			
Overall	0.015			
Wald χ^2 (7)	2413.56			
Prob (χ^2)	0.000			
Multicollinearity	1.23			
Heteroskedasticity	15469.94			
Serial Correlation	148.49			
F-statistics	$F(45,355)=191.44$			

Table 2: GMM results on Institutional Quality and Life Expectancy

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	z-value	Prob> z
Constant	0.221	0.013	16.60	0.000*
<i>RLI</i>	0.002	0.000	65.63	0.000*
<i>CI</i>	0.000	0.000	2.21	0.027*
<i>BQI</i>	0.001	0.000	2.35	0.019*
<i>PRI</i>	0.002	0.000	6.70	0.000*
<i>HE</i>	0.000	0.000	0.93	0.351
<i>LAB</i>	0.000	0.000	31.21	0.000*
<i>INFR</i>	-4.230	1.520	-2.78	0.006*
Diagnostic Statistics:				
Wald	$\chi^2_8 = 473856.050$			
Prob (χ^2)	0.000			
Sargan test	$\chi^2_{34} = 26.913$			
Prob> $\chi^2 =$	0.469			
Arellano-Bond				
	Order	Z		Prob>Z
	1.	0.115		0.908
	2.	2.400		0.164

Note: * and ** indicates significance at 5 and 10 percent level of significance

Notably, property right is statistically significant at five percent but with negative coefficient. In other words, one percent increase in property rights regulations on average leads to 0.04 percent decrease on life expectancy in the region. Considering the instrumental variables,

apart from labour force which is statistically insignificant, the other two variables are positively and statistically significant at one percent.

Similarly, various diagnostic checks were performed and the results are shown in Table 1; these include the results of multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation. However, the post estimation has shown that the model does not have issues with either heteroscedasticity or autocorrelation. In addition for robustness check, GMM results are also shown in Table 1. The coefficient of *RLI* is positive and it is statistically significant at one percent level of significant. It means that one percent increase in effective rule of law policies in SSA countries on average leads to 0.002 percent increase on life expectancy in the region. Nevertheless, this situation is in consonance with human capital development theory. Therefore the implementation of rule of law policy is expected to influence the life expectancy of the people positively. This assertion is supported by previous studies such as [9, 35]. They are of the opinion that health is an intertwining factor, that the conditions in which people live affect their level of contribution to national growth in any given society.

Furthermore, corruption index exhibits a positive relationship with life expectancy in the region of study. It is statistically significant at ten percent. In other words, a one percent increases in control of corruption in SSA countries on average leads to 0.001 percent increase on life expectancy in the region. This result is also in consonance with human capital development theory and is supported by previous studies such as [36], using a cross country panel data analysis, found that a one percent rise in life expectancy at birth increases the years of schooling by 3.5 percent, which can influence income positively.

In another scenario, bureaucratic quality index is statistically significant at ten percent with positive coefficient. In other words, a one percent increase in effective bureaucratic qualities leads to 0.001 percent increase on life expectancy in SSA countries. This finding is consistent with economic theory and also supported by previous researchers like [37, 4]. They opined that countries score high in life expectancy when bureaucratic quality is effective and free from renege on the part of the government's policies in power.

Property rights show that it is statistically significant at five percent with a positive coefficient. This implies that, one percent increase in property right regulations in SSA countries, on average leads to increase of about 0.002 percent on life expectancy within the region of research area. This implies that as the level of the freedom of property rights increases, the life expectancy of the people among the countries of this study rises. This result is in line with economic theory and is supported by recent studies such as [23]. He finds evidence that exogenous improvements in institutional quality have positive and statistically significant impact on life expectancy. Also by symmetry, developing countries have higher payoffs when improving institutional quality.

In a similar vein, all the control variables are statistically significant at five percent with positive coefficient except infrastructural facilities which is negative. Insofar, these variables have role to play to actualize high level of life expectancy in SSA countries. The forth model related to the impact of institutional quality on life expectancy in the entire region of SSA countries. The *LEX* model has passed the Sargan test of over identifying restrictions and Arellano-Bond for autocorrelation respectively and also shown on Table 1 as in the previous model.

The result of Hausman test indicates that REM is more appropriate for the analysis. From the REM results of the model show that the coefficient of *RLI* is positively and statistically significant at five percent level of significance. In other words, one percent increase in the implementation of rule of law index in the region on average leads to 0.002 percent increase on life expectancy of the people. This result is in line with human capital development theory. In other words, effective enforcement/implementation of rule of law in SSA countries leads to a multiplier effect on the entire economy and life expectancy in particular. This finding is consistent with the assertion given by previous studies such as [29] that effective rule of law determines the extent of protection and enforcement of legal rights of the citizens and foreigners alike including corporate entities leads to higher standard of living of the citizens.

In view of corruption index, it shows that the coefficient is negatively related to life expectancy, and it is statistically insignificant. This situation does not agree with human development theory. This finding lends support to the ones reported by previous studies such as [10, 30, 31, 32]. They assert that pervasive corruption in an economy can reinforce existing economic and social inequalities as well as intensify the depth of poverty and reduce the access by vulnerable segments of society to the basic needs of life. This situation painted here is very glaring in the SSA countries in general and low-income SSA countries in particular.

Considering the *BQI*, it is statistically insignificant with a negative coefficient. In other words, this result is not in support of human development theory. This could be as a result of poor implementation of bureaucratic quality in the area of study. [33, 34] assert that the quality of contract enforcement, the police and the courts as well as the development of human resources vis-à-vis life expectancy in all ramifications are basic ingredient for rapid development in any given country or region.

CONCLUSION

The study makes use of recent data in examining the impact of institutional quality on life expectancy in Low-income sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries. This study uses the system GMM estimation to estimate life expectancy. This technique enabled this study to handle the potential endogeneity problems and to obtain consistent estimates. One way to raise income levels in SSA countries is through increased investments in education. According to World Bank (2014) pointed out that higher education is very crucial in increasing life expectancy and development. Since life expectancy is correlated with viable institutions like rule of law, hence appropriate institutional policies are important to development process.

Due to the fact that attaining good institutional quality in every aspect of the economy is practically impossible for SSA countries in general. Therefore government should concentrate their efforts on some institutional quality such as improvement on rule of law, corruption, property right and effective bureaucratic quality which are found to be most important for life expectancy in Low-income sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries.

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Abbreviation:

BQ:	Bureaucratic Quality
CI:	Corruption
DOLS:	Dynamic Ordinary Least Square
EDU:	Educational Attainment
FMOLS:	Fully Modified Ordinary Least Square
GDP:	Gross Domestic Product
GE	Government Expenditure
GMM:	Generalized Method Of Moments
HC:	Human Capital
HE:	Hospital Expenditure
INFR:	Infrastructural Facilities
LAB:	Labour Force
LEX:	Life Expectancy
OECD:	Organization Economic Community Development
OLS:	Ordinary Least Square
PCSE:	Panel Corrected Standard Error
PCY:	Per Capita Income
PRI:	Property
REM:	Random Effect Model
RLI:	Rule of Law
SE:	School Expenditure
SSA:	Sub-Saharan Africa
VAR:	Vector Autoregressive

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